

UP2030

Urban Planning and design ready for 2030

Cities in Action Shaping just, resilient & climate neutral urban planning Session Notes

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This project has received funding from the Horizon Innovation Actions under the grant agreement n° 101096405.

SCAN QR CODE

About UP2030:

UP2030 is dedicated to aiding cities in achieving climate neutrality through enhanced urban planning and design. The project introduces the innovative 5UP approach to support city stakeholders and local authorities in integrating climate-neutral strategies into their everyday actions and long-term planning. Focused on promoting spatial justice and inclusive participation, UP2030 empowers communities and local governments to become agents of change, driving socio-technical transitions that enhance urban liveability and sustainability. The project's strategy aims to produce actionable insights and scalable solutions for urban environments, prioritizing resilience, equity, and sustainable urban development.

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Session Title: Tools for Blue & Green Infrastructures and Climate Resilience

Date/Time: 03.11.2025 – 16:10-17:40

Session Moderator(s): Giacomo Blanco

Note-Taker Name: Giacomo Blanco

General Notes:

The session gathered approximately 20 participants and focused on a suite of tools developed by LINKS, LNEC, DELTARES, and AQUATEC to support climate resilience, water-smart planning, and nature-based blue and green infrastructure.

The session combined short technical presentations with an interactive Tool Fair, allowing participants to engage directly with tool providers.

Participants showed interest in the practical application of the tools, particularly regarding data requirements, implementation strategies, and real case studies.

Session Objectives/Focus:

The session aimed to:

- Present a diverse set of blue & green infrastructure and climate resilience tools and demonstrate their potential applications in urban contexts.
- Enable hands-on interaction with tool providers through the Tool Fair.
- Gather participant feedback through a live survey to understand perceived relevance, clarity, and collaboration interest.
- Explore opportunities for future cooperation and use of the tools in real city contexts.

Key Discussion Points:

- Presentations provided an overview of tools related to air quality forecasting, ecosystem services, climate risk assessment, resilience evaluation, water-smartness, and water reuse.
- During the Tool Fair, participants asked about data needs, compatibility with municipal workflows, and potential use in their cities.
- Interest emerged around the complementarity of tools and how they can support integrated climate adaptation strategies.

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Important Quotes:

No quote was captured, as the audience's questions and comments occurred mainly during one-to-one interactions.

Important Stories / Concrete Achievements:

Contact exchanges took place between participants and speakers, suggesting potential collaboration avenues.

Primary Outcomes:

- Perceived relevance: Participants rated the tools as highly relevant for supporting urban climate resilience, with an average score of 4 out of 5.
 - Clarity: The presentations were considered generally clear and understandable, with mid-high comprehension scores.
 - Interest in collaboration: Respondents expressed interest in exploring future collaborations with all presenting partners.
 - Engagement: The Tool Fair format encouraged personalised conversations and sparked several potential follow-up contacts.
 - Added value: Participants appreciated seeing multiple tools addressing complementary aspects of climate resilience.
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Session Title: Data Governance and digital planning

Date/Time: 03.11.2025 – 16:10-17:40

Session Moderator(s): Will Brown

Note-Taker Name:

Session Objectives/Focus:

This workshop intends to bring together tool providers and cities/potential future collaborators. It will be structured around an initial run of 5 minute presentations by each tool provider (Buro Happold, TSPA, UCCRN and UCAM), to summarise tool use and technical elements and talk about their case studies.

This will then be followed by a series of small group discussions between tool providers and cities – pairing cities and tool providers who did not work together, to clarify and discuss the challenges and benefits of developing tools through collaboration. This will then be followed by a general discussion around the universal challenges and opportunities presented by such collaboration. The final section, will form a discussion which focuses on insights from working with cities to develop potential future paths of development of each tool and how there could be future collaborations between tool providers and other organisations going forward.

General Notes:

Well attended session.

Representation from Belfast, Budapest and Muenster, as well as from Barcelona

Discussions went to plan. We split the group into two halves to discuss a series of pre-determined questions concerning the collaboration between tool provider and cities.

Eloise Deshayes (UIC) presented their under development tool benchmarking tool. This was well received by the city representatives.

We covered all our objectives within the allotted time.

Key Discussion Points:

The role of data siloisation in decision making

The balance between technical accuracy and tool useability – with an interesting discussion at the end regarding the value of tools not only being rooted in their accuracy, but also in their ability to actually be effectively embedded in decision making.

The overreliance on data in decision making – wariness of implicitly trusting data/modelling within urban processes.

Important Quotes:

Important Stories / Concrete Achievements:

The barriers of combined data and organisational silos within urban governance discussed between representatives from Barcelona and Budapest

Primary Outcomes:

Open discussion about effectively situating tools and data within urban governance.

Session Title: Scaling Up Urban Climate Solutions for achieving climate neutrality

Date/Time: 03.11.2025 – 16:10-17:40

Session Moderator(s): Elena Petsani (ICLEI)

Speaker(s): Elena Petsani, Imanol Ugalde, Marcel Gutenberger (ICLEI), Till Sterzel (GreenAdapt), Julia Bartsch, Daria Ivleva, Frédérique Tougas (adelphi), Diana Kupper (GGGI), Nor Jihane Touati (UIC)

Note-Taker Name: no notetaker assigned, because of the nature and the structure of the session.

General Notes:

The session took place on the plenary room Pau Gil, in parallel to other 4 sessions. The session was attended by approximately 20 people, excluding speakers.

A Slido was set up for collecting the main reflections from the audience at the end of the session, after the presentations and a detail explanation about each of the tools was given. The responses were shown on the screen.

Another Slidos were created for each of the breakout groups, in order to collect feedback from the participants, but they were not used in the end, in order to not disrupt the flow of interaction with them. Participants provided their comments and feedback orally in the breakout sessions.

Session Objectives/Focus:

This workshop presents tested tools, financial models, and governance strategies from the Horizon Europe UP2030 project. Designed for urban planners, municipal leaders, and solution providers, it offers practical pathways to expand demonstration projects into investable, city-scale interventions. These resources will offer cities, urban planners, technical providers, and urban investors a clear, actionable roadmap for navigating the complex upscaling process.

The session was divided in two main parts:

- In the first part there was a round of presentations where an overview of the platforms and tools that were developed as part of the upscaling was provided.
- In the second part, participants were divided in 4 groups to go into a more detailed explanation of the following tools/platforms:
 - o Group 1: Urban Typologies with Till, Frédérique & Julia
 - o Group 2: Governance Tool with Daria
 - o Group 3: CBA Guide and Green Finance Guide with Diana
 - o Group 4: MOOC with Nor

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Key Discussion Points:

- Overall presentation of the main solutions developed in UP2030 as part of the upscaling activities: UP2030 Service Platform and MOOC.
- Discussion on Urban Typologies, led by GreenAdapt and adelphi.
- Discussion on Transformative Governance Tool, led by adelphi.
- Discussion on Cost and Benefit Analysis guide, and Green Finance Guide, led by GGGI.
- Discussion on the MOOC, led by UIC.
- Collection of general feedback about the Service Platform and the MOOC

Important Quotes:

- In order to respond to the needs of upscaling and create an enabling environment in cities, two main instruments were developed: UP2030 Service Platform and the Massive Online Open Course (MOOC). Both of them will be finalised by the end of the project.
- The UP2030 Service Platform is directly connected to the upscaling approach that UP2030 cities implemented in the last phase of the project. The platform collects information about the methodology used and best practices from cities, so that the platform users can obtain practical guidance on how to develop an upscaling plan in its own local context.
- The MOOC aims to create bridges between scientific advancements and climate governance and planning. The primary aim is to empower city practitioners with the knowledge, skills, and tools necessary for integrating the principles of carbon neutrality, climate resilience, and spatial justice into their urban planning practices.

Important Stories / Concrete Achievements:

More than 100+ videos have been created for the MOOC, containing theoretical videos, technical videos of tools and case study videos. The MOOC will soon be available in all European languages.

A governance assessment was conducted in the city of Budapest in an in-person workshop, which helped the city map their goals and points of improvement when it comes to governance structures.

The finance guides (CBA Guide and Green Finance Guide) provide solutions tailored to the needs, high-level contexts and project characteristics of the city.

Urban Typologies grouped EU regions at NUTS-3 level based on the analysis of 29 indicators. These typologies aim to foster the transfer of measures between regions and cities in Europe.

Primary Outcomes:

- Participants were provided with direct access to practical tools and tested frameworks for scaling pilot projects.
 - Insights into the political, institutional, and financial enablers of successful upscaling were shared in the session.
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- Transferable lessons were shared to support strategic planning and investment-readiness for climate-neutral urban interventions.

Feedback to enhance the usability and functionality of the UP2030 Service platform (and its tools) and the MOOC was collected from participants.

Session Title: Spatial Justice through Participatory Planning: Designing a Just Participatory Process

Date/Time: 03.11.2025 – 16:10-17:40

Session Moderator(s) and Organizers: Juliana E. Goncalves, Roberto Rocco, Maria Sitzoglou, Nafsika Michail, Diana Kupper, Stelios Grafakos, Milutin Djuraskovic, Nick Pantelidis, Alexandros Gkatsikos, Stefanos Vrochidis, Alberto D. Seoane, Alice Jelmini, Taliah Dommerholt, Samir Amin, Cristina Visconti, Louise Francis

Note-Taker Name: Juliana E. Goncalves

General Notes:

As part of the UP2030 project's closing event, Task 3.4 organised a workshop titled "Spatial Justice through Participatory Planning: Designing a Just Participatory Process". The interactive workshop brought together urban planners, designers, and researchers to explore how participatory planning can advance spatial justice in cities. Using real or fictitious urban cases, participants were able to experiment with linking UP2030 tools to various planning phases, from visioning to piloting, while critically reflecting on how these tools shape spatial justice outcomes. An interactive poster exercise invited participants to contribute insights and structured feedback on participatory strategies derived from ten UP2030 partner cities. The poster was based on the findings from the research carried out in Task 3.4 - the goal was to understand whether our project insights resonate with a broader audience.

Session Objectives/Focus:

- Enable participants to design participatory processes guided by strategic planning theory and grounded in spatial justice.
- Explore how participation tools align with planning phases and spatial justice dimensions.
- Collect structured feedback on strategies for participatory planning via a poster.
- Build a network to exchange and disseminate practical strategies for participatory planning.

Key Discussion Points:

NA. It was a workshop.

Important Quotes:

NA. It was a workshop.

Important Stories / Concrete Achievements:

NA.

Primary Outcomes:

The workshop demonstrated that the workshop structure was effective: participants were able to link UP2030 tools to different stages of the planning cycle and describe spatial justice implications of their choices. More than completing this structured exercise, participants engaged in meaningful, in-depth discussions about the participatory planning and spatial justice. These exchanges showed a strong capacity to critically unpack how tools can both enable and constrain just outcomes in practice.

The interactive poster exercise further confirmed some insights of this deliverable, with the survey-style exit responses showing strong agreement on several key points. Across the contributions, three participatory strategies emerged as the most widely supported, indicating clear shared priorities among participants. They are:

- Build capacity for participation through training, networks, and hubs and inter-city learning platforms
- Create coalitions across sectors and governance levels to support long-term participation
- Incorporate continuous feedback and reflection to improve participatory practices over time

Overall, the results suggest that the insights developed in UP2030 resonate strongly with a broader audience and that the approach successfully fosters critical and justice-oriented reflection on participatory planning.

Session Title: Digital tools supporting building decarbonization in an urban context

Date/Time: 03.11.2025 – 16.10 to 17.40

Session Moderator(s): Prof. Ipek Gürsel Dino Middle East Technical University, Ms. İlkim Canlı Akyol ODTÜ-GÜNAM

Note-Taker Name: Michael Bourmpos, Maggioli

General Notes:

This session presented the Integrated Digital Twin, a suite of digital tools designed to support the decarbonization of the built environment.

Session Objectives/Focus:

This session focused on how simulation on building energy renovation from 2025 to 2050 through the use of digital twin tools can lead to informed decision making. It included demonstrations and discussion on how digital, data-driven solutions can accelerate the transition to climate-neutral buildings. A brainstorming part within the session engaged the audience into meaningful discussions with respect to the proposed digital tool.

Key Discussion Points:

Professor Ipek Gürsel Dino started the session introducing the speakers and giving an overview of the agenda. She then went on to present the work done by UBEM on AI-powered decision-making for energy renovation planning.

Miguel Gomez Meiras from CIRCE gave a presentation on “District CO2 Life Cycle Assessment for Retrofit: Evaluating carbon emissions throughout retrofit project stages”.

Kostas Kalaboukas from Maggioli SPA followed, presenting how MIRA digital twin platform was adapted to visualize the results from the 4 different retrofit scenarios regarding energy and GHG emissions reduction.

Pierre Navaro Auburtin the gave a presentation on ETH Zurich’s Circular Urban Planning tool and its application to the city of Lisbon.

A Q&A session followed where clarifications were given on the methodology and the results for the retrofit scenarios simulations.

Berfin Kahraman from Istanbul then spoke about the work done in the past three years and how the presented tools can be important for informed decision making. A discussion followed on stakeholders possibly interested in the bundle of tools. Energy companies as well as technology companies (related to energy) were identified as strong candidates.

A brainstorming session followed with two different thematic, 1) Integrated digital tools (simulations, artificial intelligence, GIS...) and digital twins, 2) Life cycle assessment and circularity. The aim was to answer the following questions:

- How can the thematic support the planning and design phases for cities' decarbonization?
- What are the key features and functionalities that stakeholders require from the thematic for effectively implementing decarbonization initiatives?
- What are the potential challenges and barriers in implementing the thematic for cities' decarbonization, and how can these be addressed?
- How can the 5 UP approaches be addressed by the thematic? Who are the relevant stakeholders?
- The two groups produced two canvases with answers and considerations on the thematic.

Important Quotes:

There is no one single "BEST" solution. Optimal choices depend on a balance of KPIs.

Data-driven planning and collaboration enable healthier, equitable, and resilient cities.

Data availability and engagement of cities officials are necessary for successful implementation.

Important Stories / Concrete Achievements:

Data acquisition and generation.

Bundle of digital tools for building decarbonization.

Standalone tools that can be further exploited.

Primary Outcomes:

Tools can be used as standalone but also integrated and bundled as one.

Istanbul feels positive for the future exploitation of the tools and the impact on decision making.

Session Title: "The Tale of Two Cities": Participation and Engagement Tools for Urban Planning - Experiences from Budapest and Belfast

Date/Time: 03.11.2025 – 13.25-14.55

Session Moderator(s): Diana Kupper (GGGI) and Louise Francis (CM)

Note-Taker Name: -

General Notes:

The discussion proceeded by outlining each city's goals and background, the challenges/themes, the approach to community engagement, the results, the lessons learned, and the way forward.

Session Objectives/Focus:

The session introduced and discussed type of stakeholder engagement used in the two cities for urban planning. It introduced various participatory tools used by the cities in engaging local citizens. The tools that were presented and discussed include, Community Maps, developed by Mapping for Change, the Safer Routes to School Toolkit, developed by Design Clips, and the Storytelling tool from the Institute for Urban Excellence (the latter is yet to be implemented in Budapest). Cities shared and discussed their unique experiences in implementing these tools and highlighted common themes and lessons from tailoring these tools to their local contexts.

Key Discussion Points:

- City goals, background
- The Challenge
- The approach to community engagement
- The results
- The lessons learned
- The way forward

Important Quotes:

- Despite the differences between the two cities, we identified common themes, opportunities and challenges in engaging local communities

Important Stories / Concrete Achievements:

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Strengthened collaboration between communities and local municipalities were observed – especially in Belfast, where city officials engaged in various ways with the local community in the pilot neighbourhood.

Budapest empowered its public transportation company and local districts with the community engagement tools provided by UP2030, ensuring that local citizens are involved in the planning of healthy streets initiatives.

Primary Outcomes:

Exchanged experiences of implementing participatory planning tools in the cities and deduced key lessons learned and steps forward to using these tools beyond the UP2030 project.

Session Title: City ClimaQuiz – Discover the Prototypes of Thessaloniki, Lisbon and Rio de Janeiro

Date/Time: 03.11.2025 – 13.25-14.55

Session Moderator(s): Irene Tsakiridou, Athina Chontolidou, Dimitra Zouni, Maria Charalampoglou

Lisbon: Maria João Telhado, Pedro Teixeira, Rui Mendes, Maria Adriana Cardoso, Maria do Céu Almeida

Rio de Janeiro: Cristina Visconti, Mattia Leone

Note-Taker Name: -

General Notes:

The session blends learning, play, and collaboration — with short team activities, audience reflection, and interaction.

Session Objectives/Focus:

The session aims to present the approaches and prototypes developed by the cities of Thessaloniki, Lisbon, and Rio de Janeiro in the framework of the UP2030 project, with a focus on climate action at district level.

Through a structured, yet interactive format, the session promoted peer-to-peer exchange, enhance knowledge transfer among city stakeholders, and foster engagement through participatory learning methods.

By combining concise presentations with gamified elements, the session supported deeper understanding of the challenges, methodologies, and potential replicability of the pilot actions across diverse urban contexts.

Key Discussion Points:

Thessaloniki, Lisbon, and Rio de Janeiro presented key facts about their pilot areas, the climate issues they are addressing, and the prototypes developed within the UP2030 project. You will hear stories rooted in the local context — about what worked, what did not, and what they are trying next.

Important Quotes:

Integrating Tools and Decisions

What we've seen across the three pilots is how technical and digital tools — like climate assessments and monitoring systems — can support planners in making informed decisions. But it's also clear that the tools only create real impact when they're used in real contexts, connecting data with lived experience.

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What stands out is that these tools have meaning only when they are integrated into local planning. Data needs to speak to the realities of people and places, transforming from analysis into guidance for design and policy.

Important Stories / Concrete Achievements:

The results of the initial quiz, that worked as an ice breaker, point to a strong shared perception of climate urgency: most participants feel that climate impacts are already evident in their cities, while acknowledging that local climate plans remain largely confined to words or small pilot initiatives, with limited visible transformation on the ground. Focusing on water thematic, estimates of domestic water consumption from the participants show a reasonably accurate awareness, despite notable dispersion. Finally, the metaphors chosen to describe climate adaptation — invoking slowness, bureaucracy, or recurring challenges — reinforce the idea that implementation is falling short of both needs and expectations.

Thessaloniki presented the District Climate Action Plan (DCAP) for Dioikitirion—its first neighborhood-scale climate strategy—designed not only to tackle environmental challenges but to reimagine urban life from the ground up. Aligned with the city’s Climate City Contract, the DCAP envisions Dioikitirion as a greener, more accessible, and climate-friendly neighborhood. Through an inclusive co-creation process involving residents, municipal departments, experts, civil society, and the academic community, the plan proposes integrated interventions rooted in local realities: expanding urban greenery, promoting renewable energy, reshaping public space, and reactivating underused areas. By combining environmental ambition with social participation, the process established Dioikitirion as a prototype for equitable, community-led climate planning in dense, historic urban districts—a model for how cities can transform climate action into everyday urban experience.

With the support of the [Neutrality Story Map](#) (NSM) tool, the presentation illustrated the current challenges faced by the Dioikitirion district—such as aging, energy-inefficient buildings, a lack of green public spaces, and the widespread occupation of sidewalks by parked vehicles. Key aspects of the co-creation process were highlighted, as well as the integration of community insights into spatial and climate planning.

Lisbon presented its “StepUPLxALL” prototype, centred on the Alvalade parish, where the city’s vision of becoming sustainable, resilient and inclusive underpins its goal of achieving climate neutrality by 2030. The city highlighted how the four local pilots – Coruchéus Library, Alvalade Market, São Miguel Rugby Club and the National Civil Engineering Laboratory (LNEC) – serve as living laboratories to test solutions for energy efficiency, smart water management, circularity, sustainable mobility and climate resilience. Community participation was emphasised as a core pillar, supported by digital tools, neutrality story maps, a neighbourhood walking route and sustainable event practices that strengthen citizen engagement. Lisbon also stressed the importance of replicating these solutions across other parishes, aligning its work with the Climate City Contract 2030 and reinforcing cross-sector collaboration to scale the transformative impact of the Prototype.

Rio de Janeiro prototype has been developed by UCCRN and Deltares implemented tools to respond respectively on heat and flooding risks and both partners presented the results.

UCCRN applied the Urban Design Climate Workshop (UDCW) methodology to support the creation of a 2050 urban scenario integrating advanced climate simulations, with a focus on the district of São Cristóvão. The focus of UCCRN has been downscaling the Sustainability Corridors of PDS- Sustainable Development

and Climate Action Plan Linking general objectives with locally grounded design strategies. Deltares focused on advancing flood resilience implementing hydraulic flood modelling and adaptive strategies for urban flood resilience for Rio's Acari River basin. Both Partners worked with City of Rio engaging city departments in capacity building, training and dissemination activities. The presentation focused on technical achievements of tool applications and synergies with stakeholders and potential upscaling.

Primary Outcomes

- Generating Awareness through climate quiz
 - Many municipalities face challenges with fragmented data or limited internal expertise. Building capacity within local teams — the ability to use, interpret, and adapt tools — is fundamental. This isn't just a technical task, but an investment in institutional learning and long-term resilience.
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Session Title: From Vision to Action: From Ideas to Realisation, Obstacles and Adaptation in Istanbul & Zagreb

Date/Time: 03.11.2025 – 13.25-14.55

Session Moderator(s): Prof.Dr. İpek GÜRSEL DİNO, Berfin KAHRAMAN

Note-Taker Name: Berfin KAHRAMAN

General Notes:

This session was planned to bring together two UP2030 cities – Istanbul and Zagreb – to share how they moved from idea to realisation, and how they adapted to obstacles along the way. However, due to the Zagreb city presenter not attending the meeting, only İstanbul presented its studies.

Istanbul presented its work on modelling the solar potential of buildings, integrating micromobility solutions, and designing climate-friendly urban furniture.

Session Objectives/Focus:

- Modelling the solar potential of buildings,
- Integrating micromobility solutions,
- Designing climate-friendly urban furniture,
- Knowledge share

Key Discussion Points:

What most accelerates the shift from ideas to real-life action?

What is one idea or practice from Istanbul you would adapt in your own city?

UP2030 city success impacts

Where do cities most often get stuck in the transition process?

What's the “invisible success factor” that keeps a plan from staying just on paper?

Important Quotes:

What most accelerates the shift from ideas to real-life action? 9 / 14

What is one idea or practice from Istanbul or Zagreb you would adapt in your own city? 7 / 14 7

- Data collection
- Seaside
- Useful urban furniture
- Working on the solar panel installation on old and new buildings
- Clean energy transition through urban furniture
- The urban furniture for solar energy production
- More digitalisation in terms of data collection and monitoring

F Rank the following according to their impact on UP2030 city success 10 / 14

- > 1 Support of policy makers
- > 2 Multi-level governance
- > 2 Data-based monitoring systems
- > 3 Citizen partnership
- > 4 Flexible financing models

■ Where do cities most often get stuck in the transition process? 10 / 14

● What's the "invisible success factor" that keeps a plan from staying just on paper? 11

good people	Political alignment
Tangible implementations	Climate action awareness
Municipal employees	Co working coordination but a real one...
Hope for a better future	Bureaucracy
Communication network	Patience
Putting priority	

Important Stories / Concrete Achievements:

During the session, we discussed common points with other partners and guest cities. İzmir Municipality shared their similar projects and outcomes.

Primary Outcomes:

- Applications like the Istanbul pilot can be integrated into other cities on a large and small scale.
 - The biggest obstacles to implementation are a lack of authority and confusion regarding governance.
 - The rate of project implementation can be increased by using multiple governance systems.
 - The success rate can increase with the support of policymakers and the completion of regulatory gaps.
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Session Title: Paving the Way: Strategic Integration of Climate Resilience in Urban Design and Planning through the co-creation of methodologies and guidelines

Date/Time: 03.11.2025 – 13:25-14:55

Session Moderator(s): Ms Montserrat Martínez, Aquatec.

Note-Taker Name: Ms Sarah Tosca Levy, Ms Judit Tarradellas, Ms Virgínia Domingo

General Notes:

Welcome & presentation of the agenda's session (in Spanish)

Speaker: Mr Francesc Arolas, Granollers city councillor

Mr Francesc Arolas opened the session by welcoming the participants and speakers and presented the vision of Granollers for a greener and more inclusive city: co-creation with citizens is a central element of this vision. The UP2030 project was a great opportunity to strengthen this vision with experimentation, prototyping and citizen engagement.

Pitches from cities

City of Milan. Speakers: Ms Eleonora Esposito and Ms Sarah Tosca Levy, Milan city council

Summary of the pitch

Eleonora Esposito and Sarah Tosca Levy presented the Ecosystem services Assessment Methodology that was developed in the framework of UP2030, an approach to guide municipal urban design and planning towards climate neutrality.

Through an analysis of the city's internal processes, Milan illustrated the challenges and opportunities encountered, with a focus on four key dimensions: data governance, to ensure the quality and transparency of information; the involvement of internal stakeholders, to build shared languages and processes; the transition from data to strategic planning, with a focus on upscaling good practices; the reliability and accountability of methods, to ensure scientific soundness. The aim is to show how measuring and valuing the benefits provided by urban nature can form the basis for more resilient and integrated urban policies.

Pilot Overview: From measuring ecosystem services to strategic planning: challenges and opportunities for urban climate neutrality

Eleonora Esposito first explained how the specific focus and objectives of UP2030 were defined in the context of Milan: this was done by engaging multiple departments within the Municipality to address existing gaps and emerging needs. In this phase, a need for better knowledge and methodologies for ecosystem services assessment to support urban planning and design has been identified.

Ecosystem services are the multiple benefits provided by ecosystems to humankind: urban cooling, carbon storage and sequestration, flood risk mitigation, etc. In urban contexts, green and blue infrastructures contribute greatly to ecosystem services provision.

Therefore, for the city of Milan, the specific objective within the UP2030 has been to build a solid and replicable methodology to assess the impacts of urban plans and projects on the provision of ecosystem services in the city.

Some initial criteria were set to build a replicable methodology within the Municipality: the method must be based on a reliable and open-source tool, already used by other public administrations.

This led to the selection of the model InVEST (Integrated Valuation of Ecosystem Services and Tradeoffs), an open-source tool developed by the Stanford University. The City of Milan worked with LINKS Foundation of Torino (Italy) to build and test a customized methodology based on InVEST tool.

Sarah Tosca Levy presented the key features of the InVEST model. InVEST can provide the biophysical and economic value of ecosystem services provided by natural capital, highlighting changes resulting from urban transformations (loss or increase of the services chosen by the user); it assesses ecosystem services on a spatial basis, assigning a specific value to each land-use category.

A great effort was made to gather the most solid and qualitative input data for the model: it was important to use local, up-to-date and reliable data, and if possible, already used and owned by the Municipality for other plans and projects. This effort on input data was not only done for technical purposes, as the quality of the input data affects the quality of the output data; but mostly for governance and managerial purposes, as good quality of input data is the main condition for the tool and methodology to be credible and replicable inside the Municipality. In that sense, working with an Italian technical and liaison partner like Fondazione LINKS really helped in gathering local and reliable data in the territorial context of Milan.

Milan decided to test and build the InVEST-based methodology for two specific ecosystem services: urban cooling and carbon storage and sequestration capacity of urban green areas. These two ecosystem services were selected because they are in line with Municipal priorities and ongoing plans.

The outputs generated by InVEST when applied at the urban, neighbourhood and street scale were maps provided geo-referenced information on the biophysical and economic value of green spaces for the specific ecosystem services assessed. Together with LINKS, it was decided to take a further step: a report was produced to explain the results and their implications for planning, as well as an internal handbook to describe how to use the InVEST tool, which data is needed, and how to update this data.

These outputs were the result of continuous dialogue and joint work between municipal technicians and LINKS. Every decision was carefully discussed, tested and sometimes revised. This was a process of mutual and ongoing learning for both the Municipality and LINKS.

Key take-aways

For Eleonora Esposito and Sarah Tosca Levy, the whole experience was successful: for the first time, the Municipality addressed the topic of ecosystem services as a practical approach to guide urban planning and design. The concept of ecosystem services has been brought into internal technical discussions, leading to a cultural shift on how to approach urban greenery.

This happened because from the beginning the focus was put on an area where there was a real and growing need for better knowledge and tools.

Another important element has been the dialogue established with Milan's scientific community (universities and research centers) to discuss, validate and refine the InVEST-based methodology.

Also, producing ready-to-use outputs like the report and handbook has ensured that the methodology would be replicated overtime, while also making it easier to communicate the project's outcomes with different municipal offices.

To conclude the pitch session, Eleonora Esposito shared some lessons learned relevant for other cities, technical partners and consultants when trying to bring innovation into public administrations.

The first lesson is that any new method or tool need/must be adapted to the local context: data must be reliable, accessible and regularly updated. This ensures not only the quality of the results but also the possibility of replication after the project, essential to have the municipal staff onboard.

Another lesson to keep in mind is that each model has its strengths and limitations: for instance, for the assessment of urban cooling service, InVEST seems to be more effective for urban and neighborhood-scale planning, for comparing current and future scenarios and evaluating masterplans, while it is less suitable for micro-scale analyses. The solution is not to abandon the tool, but to integrate it with complementary models already in use or in development.

But above all, the main lesson is that having a strong technical method is not enough: it is equally important to create organizational and strategic conditions for it to be effectively used in decision-making processes, making sure to bring the methodology when windows of opportunity open (for instance for Milan, in the framework of the upcoming Green Plan) and being careful to find the right balance between technical solidness and strategic relevance, between innovation and practicality. For Eleonora Esposito, this is exactly what allows tools like InVEST to truly inform public decisions and improve the quality of cities.

City of Granollers. Speaker: Ms Judit Tarradellas, Granollers city council

Summary of the pitch

Judit Tarradellas illustrated the Granollers' approach to integrate climate resilience in the urban design and planning processes of the city. The presentation consisted of three parts: first, the followed process has been detailed, highlighting the needs, challenges, and opportunities encountered during participatory stakeholder engagement. The second part focused on the use of technological tools to design new urban developments that address climate and social vulnerabilities. Finally, the third part has shown how this knowledge has been localized into a style guide to effectively drive local action, essentially upscaling Granollers' findings.

Pilot overview: Advancing Climate Resilience in Urban Development

Granollers is actively integrating climate resilience into its urban planning strategies, particularly in the context of new developments. The city's approach was showcased through its participation in the 5UP process, a collaborative framework aimed at enhancing sustainability and adaptability in urban environments.

Granollers' journey through the 5UP process highlighted several key dimensions. First, three main needs were identified: strengthening climate resilience in new urban areas; integrating nature-based solutions and ecosystem services; enhancing cross-departmental collaboration within the municipality.

The objective for Granollers was therefore to build a technical guide to integrate climate resilience and inclusivity into the city's urban planning and design processes.

In the process, several challenges were faced, starting with the limitation of tools for assessing climate impact at the local scale and data gaps and fragmented governance structures. Another challenge consisted in finding a balance between rapid urban growth and sustainability goals.

Co-creation of solutions with local stakeholders, capacity building across municipal departments and development of replicable methodologies for other cities were the main opportunities that were unlocked during Granollers' journey, which involved more than 100 internal and external stakeholders.

During the upscaling phase, Granollers focused on expanding the pilot's impact by consolidating learnings from the pilot and embedding them into broader urban planning workflows. Three main objectives were defined for this phase: institutionalizing climate resilience in city planning, promoting interdepartmental leadership and shared ownership, and aligning strategic planning with EU climate adaptation goals. A clear leadership was defined to ensure the pilot would have an impact: the city's urban planning and environmental departments were the main promoters of the project, with strong support from political and technical leadership.

Judit Tarradellas then provided an overview of the core principles and recommendations of their Prototype for climate-resilient urban development. The technical guide has a strong scientific component, as it uses the results from the tools modelling RESCCUE and City Scan from Aquatec and TSPA as a base; the prototype has also been supported by ULab and UCCRN Climate Resilient Multi-Scale Design Studio tool, and thanks to GGGI, integrates a reflection on the use of innovative financial tools to assess the economic viability and benefits of actions associated with the implementation of the prototype, and to identify appropriate funding options.

The five core principles of the guide are the following:

- 1) Integration of ecosystem services into planning
- 2) Participatory governance and stakeholder engagement
- 3) Data-driven decision-making
- 4) Flexibility and adaptability in design
- 5) Replicability and scalability across contexts

The Strategic Recommendations of the guide span across planning, governance, data management, community involvement, and monitoring. They serve as a roadmap for embedding climate resilience into future urban projects.

The expected impact is that the guide will support drafting of urban planning documents (for instance, partial plans, urbanization projects) and enable public-private collaboration in future developments.

More information on the 2 cities' prototypes here: [UP2030 Presentation Milan Granollers.pptx](#)

Panel discussion

The workshop culminated in a panel discussion featuring leading experts. They provided diverse perspectives from the fields of climate research, public space design, and the practical implementation of urban solutions at both city and neighbourhood scales, fostering a comprehensive understanding of the challenges and opportunities ahead.

Moderator: Ms. Montse Martínez Puentes, R&D&i coordinator in Aquatec (Agbar group). Tool developer and liaison of Granollers city in UP2030-HE project.

Panelists':

Mr Francisco Rodríguez, Team Leader, Urban Transformation Lab / City, Territory & Environment at TECNALIA.

Ms Elena Domene, Head of sustainability research Area at Institut Metropolí of Autònoma Universitat of Barcelona.

Mrs. Giulia Melis, Program manager I City, Climate & Environment – Fondazione LINKS.

Q1. As service providers, you have had the opportunity to work with cities in the framework of projects, helping them enhancing the coherence between the climate agenda, and urban design and planning. Could you provide us examples of such collaborations? What were the challenges you had to face?

Contributions:

Mr Francisco Rodriguez-TECNALIA

Tecnalia is the largest centre of applied research and technological development in Spain collaborating with companies and public institutions to improve their competitiveness, people's quality of life and achieve sustainable growth.

As Team Leader within the Urban Transformation Lab of Tecnalia, Francisco Rodriguez provided an example of engagement and co-creation between citizens, local businesses and municipal stakeholders with the Horizon project drOp. The project brings together the cities of Ermua (Spain), Elva (Estonia) and Matera (Italy) to develop an integrated renovation methodology (IRM) aiming to transform social housing districts into inclusive smart neighbourhoods. In this project, citizens played a central role in defining and voting on priority projects, which included energy communities to promote local renewable energy production and shared benefits; multi-functional community centres to foster social cohesion and provide flexible public spaces; and tactical urbanism interventions focused on improving accessibility and public space usability.

He gave some insights on the opportunities and challenges of aligning climate planning with municipal plans. One of the major difficulties is that often, regulatory plans like the General Plans can be outdated, as the latter are updated every thirty years. This can make it difficult to align climate ambition with municipal plans.

The city of Vitoria-Gasteiz provides a virtuous example of such alignment, as the Municipality is currently working on the alignment between its Climate City Contract and its POUM (Municipal Urban Development Plan). This effort is important, as it ensures that new urban developments are consistent with climate adaptation and mitigation goals, and that planning processes reflect the evolving needs of the city, in terms of sustainability, inclusivity and resilience.

Francisco Rodriguez concluded its intervention with some key insights:

- Co-creation is a powerful tool for small cities to build ownership and relevance in urban projects
- Citizen engagement leads to more inclusive and impactful solutions
- Strategic alignment between climate policies and urban planning frameworks is essential for long-term success
- Flexibility and multifunctionality in urban design help cities adapt to changing social and environmental conditions

Ms Giulia Melis- Fondazione LINKS

Fondazione LINKS is a private, non-profit research institute based in Torino (Italy), and is a joint creation of Politecnico di Torino and the bank foundation Compagnia di San Paolo. It collaborates closely with academic institutions and various public administrations. With extensive experience in urban regeneration and EU-funded projects, LINKS plays a pivotal role in supporting cities through innovation and strategic planning. In particular, Fondazione LINKS was the technical and liaison partner of Milan in the framework of the UP2030 project.

Giulia Melis came back on LINKS role within the UP2030, helping Milan to build a solid and replicable methodology based on the open-source model InVEST, but also to create the conditions for a cultural shift inside the Municipality regarding ecosystem services in urban and strategic planning.

LINKS supported this transition by doing a step-by-step adaptation of the tool and method to Milan's context and available data, and by making sure the output results reflected local priorities and needs. The process began with the creation of a dedicated team within the city administration, followed by structured dialogue across departments and sectors. This collaborative approach helped identify key needs and fostered ownership of the methodology.

One of the main challenges was to make sure that the methodology would be integrated within municipal processes, and this depends on the opening of specific "windows of opportunity". In the case of Milan, the revision of the Urban Masterplan and development of a new Green Plan constituted a window of opportunity to push the InVEST-based methodology in municipal processes.

Another challenge mentioned by Giulia Melis was the importance of finding a balance between expert input (provided by the scientific community) and practical usability: simplifying the tool and the methodology is an important condition to make them accessible and actionable for city planners.

Lastly, it has been challenging to push innovation inside the Municipality: that is why LINKS promoted a multi-scale application of the methodology, to show that it could answer to a variety of needs at the urban scale, neighbourhood scale and street scale.

Giulia Melis concluded its intervention with some key insights:

- Local adaptation is essential: Tools like InVEST must be tailored to the city's governance, data, and planning frameworks
 - Cross-sector collaboration strengthens implementation and legacy
-

- Scenario-based planning helps cities anticipate future challenges and align with climate goals

Q1. As a research institute, you have a strong experience in bringing innovation and scientific support to public actors in the field of sustainability. Based on the pitches from Milan and Granollers, and the interventions of the other panellists, could you share with us some significant experiences of collaboration with local governments, and the challenges of such collaboration?

Contributions:

Ms. Elena Domene- Institut Metròpoli

Institut Metròpoli is a public consortium based in Barcelona, bringing together five universities in Barcelona, Barcelona City Council, Barcelona Provincial Council and Àrea Metropolitana de Barcelona (AMB). The mission of Institut Metròpoli is to conduct highly applied research that directly informs urban policy and planning.

The research institute places a strong emphasis on addressing inequalities, both social and environmental, which are being exacerbated by climate change. Its work aims to support municipalities in identifying vulnerable populations and areas, and in designing targeted interventions.

One of the key tools developed by Institut Metròpoli is a GIS-based Climate Change Vulnerability Indicator, which enables spatial analysis of climate risks and social vulnerabilities, municipal-level decision-making based on localized data and strategic planning for climate adaptation. This indicator was notably used by AMB to guide the design and placement of climate shelters across the metropolitan area.

Elena Domene gave some examples of the difficulties encountered in bridging research and local action. She explained that often enough, there can be a “timeframe mismatch”: academic research often operates on longer timelines than municipal planning cycles. This can hinder the alignment of research outputs with local action. She also mentioned difficulties regarding the translation of technical findings into actionable insights for diverse stakeholders (“language barrier”) and the importance data not only for research but also strategically speaking (local governments need reliable data to put a topic on the political agenda). Lastly, lack of resources impacts the capacity to fully leverage research tools, specially for smaller cities.

Elena Domene concluded its intervention with some key insights:

- Applied research must be flexible and responsive to the evolving needs of local governments
- Tools like GIS indicators can empower cities to make data-driven decisions, but require strong institutional support
- Collaboration across sectors—academia, government, and civil society—is key to addressing climate-related inequalities

Q2. You have told us about the barriers you encountered in the framework of your collaborations with cities. Could you tell us how you overcame these barriers?

Contributions:

Mr Francisco Rodríguez

Francisco Rodriguez emphasized the importance of communication between stakeholders: setting the expectations between them from the beginning and sharing the data to take aligned decisions. The development of data platforms in the context of urban regeneration projects goes in this direction.

Another way to overcome these barriers could be to act for stronger competitiveness of local governments to attract skilled professionals, especially in areas related to sustainability and digital transformation. Attracting talent could help successfully implement new technologies and methodologies within municipal structures, and lead to cultural shifts and innovation.

Lastly, Francisco Rodriguez explained how establishing indicators that connect urban planning with climate resilience strategies, could be a powerful lever to facilitate action. These common indicators should incorporate energy efficiency and neutrality parameters to guide future development. In Spain, POUMs (Municipal Urban Development Plans) are expected to undergo significant changes in the coming years, and integrating climate-focused metrics will be key to ensuring their relevance and effectiveness.

Ms Giulia Melis

Giulia Melis came back on the importance of effective communication between stakeholders and, more importantly, of building strong personal relationships and trust. In that sense, the UP2030 project proved to be a valuable opportunity to build a solid collaboration between Fondazione LINKS and the City of Milan. In particular, this collaboration has fostered a new and transformative approach within the Municipality on the topic of Ecosystem Services and the design of urban greenery: thanks to the Ecosystem Services approach, the focus is not so much on the quantity of green spaces, but more on the quality of it.

Q2. According to you, what were the levers and opportunities that were the most important to address the challenges you previously described?

Contributions:

Ms Elena Domene

For Elena Domene, building trust among stakeholders is essential for meaningful and lasting impact. Long-term collaboration thrives on open communication, shared feedback, and a commitment to transparency and mutual support throughout the process.

Also, adapting methodologies through hands-on experience allows for greater flexibility in responding to the realities of local administrations. This approach helps tailor solutions to fit available resources, institutional capacities, and planning timelines, making implementation more feasible and effective.

Finally, identifying and engaging vulnerable populations is a cornerstone of equitable urban planning. Specific methods were developed to enhance participation from diverse groups—for example, initiatives like “Vigilants de la calor” empowered citizens to monitor and respond to heat-related risks, fostering community resilience and awareness.

Session Objectives/Focus:

This event offered an insightful introduction to the UP2030 project, a Horizon Europe initiative supporting cities in their journey towards climate neutrality by leveraging urban planning and design. The session explored the project's state-of-the-art approach and the pivotal roles of its pilot cities in tackling the

different dimensions of resilient planning. Representatives of Milan and Granollers showcased their innovative solutions (prototypes) designed to enhance the coherence between climate planning and public space design. These real-world examples have demonstrated tangible strategies for cities to adapt to global changes and build resilience.

The panel discussion that followed has been an opportunity to inspire and share the practical knowledge gained from the UP2030 project's pioneering work in Milan and Granollers, demonstrating replicable approaches to tackle urban climate challenges.

Key Discussion Points:

During the panel, several questions were asked on the communication between stakeholders and, more specifically, towards citizens and more vulnerable communities.

- How can we address the diverse interests and positions of stakeholders in urban transformation processes?
- How can we measure the level of understanding among ordinary citizens—and what actions can we take to improve it?
- What strategies can empower local communities to take a more active role in shaping their urban environments?
- How can we sustain long-term mobilization of residents, especially those not typically involved in civic processes?

The panelists provided useful insights to reflect on these questions:

- Two-Way communication is essential: participation should not be top-down. Even when actions align with stakeholder demands, actively involving them in the process adds legitimacy and helps uncover deeper needs.
- Participatory processes are often difficult to implement without the active involvement of local administrations, which are frequently perceived as gatekeepers or controllers (Elena Domene mentioned the specific situation in Spain and Catalunya). Their support is vital to ensure credibility, access to resources, and institutional continuity.

Important Quotes:

Francisco Rodriguez: “Two persons sharing the same data tend to take the same decisions: this is an important quote to keep in mind for stakeholder collaboration.”

Giulia Melis “Building trust with Municipalities is key to ensure new tools and methodologies are seen as valuable assets in decision-making”.

Elena Domene: “Trust and flexibility are essential to ensure a smooth collaboration with local governments and citizens”.

Francisco Rodriguez “Even if you're doing what stakeholders ask for, including them in participatory processes is crucial to adapt goals and solutions.”

Important Stories / Concrete Achievements:

The pitch from Milan and Granollers, as well as the experience provided by the panellists, provided a variety of viewpoints on how to better align climate planning and urban planning and design.

Here is a summary of the gathered insights:

- Data-driven tools adapted to the local context for informed decision-making processes:
 - o Tools like InVEST must be tailored to the city's governance, data and planning frameworks.
 - o Tools such as RESCCUE and City Scan, among others, are useful for local governments in selecting climate-resilient solutions to help cities adapt to floods and to design new urban developments in line with climate-neutral objectives.
 - o Scenario-based planning helps cities anticipate future challenges and align with climate goals.
 - o Tools like GIS indicators, based on UP2030 KPI's, can empower cities to make data-driven decisions, but require strong institutional support.
 - o Strategic alignment between climate policies and urban planning frameworks is essential for long-term success.
- Flexibility is key:
 - o Applied research must be flexible and responsive to the evolving needs of local governments.
 - o Flexibility and multifunctionality in urban design help cities adapt to changing social and environmental conditions
- Internal and external stakeholder engagement:
 - o Cross-sector collaboration strengthens implementation and legacy.
 - o Collaboration across sectors—academia, government, and civil society—is key to addressing climate-related inequalities. The LAA methodology, used in the UP2030 participatory process, has contributed to fostering collaboration between different sectors.
 - o Co-creation is a powerful tool for small cities to build ownership and relevance in urban projects. The innovative 5UP process of the UP2030 project has demonstrated the strength of collaborative ideation.
 - o Citizen engagement leads to more inclusive and impactful solutions, and overcome certain barriers related to communication skills. Moreover, the dominance of traditional top-down behaviours has been replaced by a cross-cutting approach.

Primary Outcomes:

The session was a useful opportunity to create a dialogue between Citizens, Municipalities, Research Institutes and Technical partners in creating a link between research and local action, and in creating coherence between climatic goals and municipal processes and plans. The specific cases of Milan and Granollers provided good illustrations of such processes of collaboration, while the experience of the panellists was useful to enlarge perspectives and find common challenges and solutions.

Session Title: Climate-Resilient Neighborhoods in Existing Urban Areas – Two Cities, Two Approaches, One Goal

Date/Time: 03.11.2025 – 13.25-14.55

Session Moderator(s):

Nilo Tajuddin

From Münster: Caroline König and Alp Yilmaz

From Rotterdam: Marthe van Gils and Otto Trienekens

Note-Taker Name: -

General Notes:

As part of the **UP2030** project, the cities of **Rotterdam (Netherlands)** and **Münster (Germany)** have each developed their own **guideline for climate friendly neighborhoods thinking climate adaptation, climate neutrality, resilience and participation together** — but based on two distinct approaches:

Rotterdam followed a **case specific approach**, drawing on practical experiences from the neighborhood of **BoTu**, where parts of a climate-oriented transformation have already been implemented. These real-world insights form the basis for transferable recommendations to other areas of the city.

Münster applied a **case-overarching approach**, developing a **strategic framework and guideline** based on municipal planning structures and climate policy goals, with a strong focus on collaborative governance and citywide steering mechanisms.

Session Objectives/Focus:

Presentation of both guidelines, the opportunities and challenges of each approach, and discussion on how they can be adapted and applied in other cities and local contexts.

Key Discussion Points:

Each of these two approaches offers distinct advantages. In Rotterdam, the direct connection to and engagement with civil society was highlighted, along with a strong hands-on mentality. In Münster, the regular exchange between different municipal departments was emphasized as an important and valuable foundation—one that is further strengthened and structured through the guideline.

In addition, the question was raised as to whether the neighbourhood level truly offers advantages over an individual-building approach when it comes to implementing measures. And what this means for monitoring resilience. This led to the reflection that monitoring at neighbourhood scale may be less about

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tracking technical progress alone, and more about understanding governance dynamics, institutional collaboration, and the capacity of local actors to adapt over time.

A related discussion focused on how to engage residents who are less visible or harder to reach, and how to address vulnerability without reinforcing stigma. Positive, strengths-based engagement was emphasised in the BoTu approach as essential, recognising informal networks, local knowledge and everyday practices as core components of resilience rather than peripheral add-ons.

Possible advantages of a neighbourhood-level approach include better coordination of measures, the ability to use shared energy or green-blue infrastructure, and stronger social engagement. Challenges may arise from higher coordination needs, more complex financing, and dependence on multiple actors, which can make implementation slower and less flexible than individual-building solutions.

Another point which was raised during the workshop was that, due to the close interlinking of the UP2030 process with the Climate City Process, in Münster, the topic of climate-friendly neighborhoods can be further embedded within the city administration. Through the Cities Mission, the city has been able to firmly establish climate mitigation and climate adaptation as cross-cutting issues, creating favorable conditions for more specific topics—such as climate-friendly neighborhood development—to be well recognized and taken up.

Another issue that emerged in the discussion was the question of ownership — both among residents and within institutions. While neighbourhood-level programmes offer opportunities for collective learning and shared responsibility, they can also run the risk of becoming parallel initiatives that exist alongside municipal structures rather than being fully embedded within them. In Münster, the strong alignment between the UP2030 activities and the Climate City Process appears to create fertile ground for institutional anchoring. In BoTu, by contrast, one of the challenges was that the programme sometimes operated as an add-on to existing municipal routines, which complicated long-term integration. At the same time, BoTu demonstrated a notable strength in building local ownership and social infrastructure, with residents and community organisations taking active roles in shaping interventions. This emphasizes that resilience at the neighbourhood scale depends on distributed agency and institutional commitment, the combination of which determines whether transformation can outlive project cycles.

Important Quotes: -

Important Stories / Concrete Achievements: -

Primary Outcomes:

One outcome is that Rotterdam and Münster share similar starting conditions. Both approaches can be applied depending on the neighbourhood context and purpose, but combining elements of the two could also be highly valuable.